

Analytical application of 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene in the spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum(VI)

Tushita Babel, Saba Khan, Anita Mehta, R. S. Chauhan and A. K. Goswami*

Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001, India

E-mail : akumargoswami@rediffmail.com

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A new reagent 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of Mo^{VI} at 410 nm, in the pH range 2.3–3.3. Beer's law is obeyed in the range $(1 \text{ to } 6) \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values are $8004 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 11.98 ng cm^{-2} , respectively. The method is useful even in presence of several cations and anions.

Survey of literature reveals that the hydroxytriazenes have been used for the determination of number of transition metals¹. We report here application of 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene for spectrophotometric determination of Mo^{VI}.

Results and discussion

As revealed by study of molar composition of the complexes, it was found that Mo^{VI} forms 1 : 1 complex with 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene.

Stability constants : Harvey and Manning's method² and Purohit's method³ have been used to determine the stability constants. Validity of the methods can be confirmed from the value of $\log \beta$ obtained from both the methods. The $\log \beta$ values (4.44–4.99) agree quite well. Further the precision studies were carried out by measuring the absorbance of 10 sets of solution containing 4.79 ppm of Mo^{VI} and 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene in 1 : 5 ratio, under optimum conditions. The absorbance was measured against reagent blank at working wavelength (410 nm). Molybdenum was successfully determined at 4.79 ppm level with good precision.

Thus it can be seen that Mo^{VI} can be determined even in presence of number of ions viz. Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Co²⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₂⁻, SO₄²⁻, CO₃²⁻, PO₄³⁻, NO₃⁻, CH₃COO⁻, WO₄²⁻ present at 100 ppm level. Thus from the above studies it can be concluded that 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene can be used successfully for spectrophotometric determination of Mo^{VI}.

Experimental

3-Hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene was prepared by

using the method of Bamberger⁴.

Stock solution : A $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ stock solution of Mo^{VI} was prepared by dissolving appropriate quantity of A.R. grade molybdic acid in minimum quantity of sodium hydroxide (0.1 M) and making it up to the required volume with double-distilled water. The solution was standardized with EDTA. A $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ solution of the reagent was prepared in alcohol. Perchloric acid (1%, v/v) was prepared.

Method : Spectrum of 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene was taken in the wavelength region 387–460 nm against solvent blank. Molybdenum and 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene solutions were taken in 1 : 5 ratio and the spectrum of Mo^{VI} complex was recorded against reagent blank in the range 387–460 nm. The working wavelength was found to be 410 nm. A set of solutions containing Mo^{VI} and 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene reagent in ratio 1 : 5 was prepared and pH varied between 1 to 5. The pH range of constant maximum absorbance was found to be between 2.3 to 3.3. Composition of the complex was determined by Job's method and moles ratio method of Yoe and Jones. The study revealed that composition of Mo^{VI} complex is 1 : 1 ratio. Absorbance of set of six solutions containing Mo^{VI} to 3-hydroxy-3-*p*-tolyl-1-*m*-tolyltriazene in ratio 1 : 5 was measured at corresponding working wavelength against reagent blank. Beer's law was obeyed in concentration range 1×10^{-5} to $6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$. Interference of 22 cations and anions in the determination of Mo^{VI} was studied. To the set of solutions containing Mo^{VI} to reagent 1 : 5 ratio, 10 ppm of different foreign ions were added at optimum conditions. Absorbance was measured against reagent blank. Those ions, which did not interfere at 10 ppm level, their interference was again studied at 50 ppm level. In case no or little change in absorbance was seen as compared to

the absorbance without any foreign ion, then for those ions interference was studied again at 100 ppm level. However tolerance of still higher concentration was not studied. A UV/Vis Systronic 108 spectrophotometer and a Systronic 324 pH meter were used.

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